

**Proceedings of the Meeting of the Board of Studies in Mechanical Engineering held on
22nd April, 2017, 2.00 PM at Seminar Hall, Main Building, Srinivas University,
Mangalore**

Members Present:

1. Dr. Suma Bhat
2. Dr. Shreeprakash
3. Dr. Shankar
4. Dr. Shiva Kumar
5. Mr. Srinath Pai
6. Mr. Rakshith Kumar P

At the outset, Dr. Suma Bhat, Chairperson of the BOS in Mechanical Engineering applauded all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

Agenda-1: Introduction of Graduate program in Mechanical Engineering and preparation of scheme of instruction, scheme of examination and detailed Curriculum.

The Chairperson explained briefly about the establishment of SRINIVAS University and the programs being introduced under SRINIVAS University. She said that the university is intending to start other B Tech program in various branches of engineering. She also explained the features of CBCS/CAGP education in the University which has been committed to follow since its inception itself.

Herewith, She provided the draft syllabus of the said programs prepared by the Faculty of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY and also explained the commitment of the University in adopting CBCS-CAGP pattern of education and gave an overview of SRINIVAS University Regulations for CBCS-CAGP and requested the Board to discuss on the issue and take appropriate decision and help the university to start the said programs from the academic year 2017-18.

The BOS members discussed the agenda in detail and drafted the course curriculum including the scheme of instruction, eligibility criteria, etc. for B Tech in Mechanical Engineering and resolved as under.

Resolution:

The Board unanimously resolved to recommend to the University to introduce B Tech in Mechanical Engineering program in Srinivas University from the Academic Year 2017-18 and also recommended to adopt the Scheme of Instruction, scheme of examination and detailed Curriculum for B Tech in Mechanical Engineering drafted as per CBCS and CAGP regulations (Annexure-I, II and III).

Agenda 2: Preparation of Scheme of Examination and Pattern of Question Papers

The Chairperson explained the guidelines relating to scheme of examination /and pattern of question papers and requested the Board to work out the Scheme of Examination and decide about the pattern of question papers to be adopted for the said programs. Accordingly the Board went through the guidelines of the Scheme of Examination provided to the board and prepared the detailed scheme of examination and pattern of question papers for B Tech in Mechanical Engineering and resolved as under.

Resolution: The Board resolved to recommend to the University to accept the pattern of question papers prepared by this BOS for B Tech in Mechanical Engineering and to adopt the same in Srinivas University from the academic year 2017-18.

Agenda-3: Preparation of Panel of Examiners

The Chairperson requested the Board Members to prepare the Panel of Examiners for the 1st and 2nd Semester Examination for the B Tech in Mechanical Engineering

Resolution: The Board prepared the Panel of Examiners (internal and external) for the 1st and 2nd Semester end Examination for the B Tech in Mechanical Engineering and resolved to recommend the same to the University.

Agenda -4: Other topics discussed with the permission of the chair.

- BOS Members recommended introducing Seminar in all Semesters
- BOS Members recommended introducing industrial training (internship) in 4th Semester
- BOS members recommended giving flexibility to select soft core subjects and also give scope for fast learners.
- BOS members recommended reducing class room teaching and increasing laboratory component in curriculum.

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Dr. Suma Bhat
Chairperson

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE